

Decentralized Trust and Dynamic Batching for Multi-Domain SDN Using Blockchain

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ABSTRACT In multi-domain network environments, each domain operates with its own Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller, making it challenging to ensure secure and consistent topology management across domains. Traditional centralized logging systems fall short in providing the transparency, flexibility, and decentralized trust needed for effective collaboration between controllers. Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) offer a decentralized and immutable way to log network operations, presenting a promising solution for multi-domain SDN environments. This paper presents an approach that uses blockchain to record topology management operations such as adding, updating, and deleting devices and links across multiple SDN domains. The framework leverages permissioned blockchains to establish decentralized trust, with SDN controllers acting as validator nodes to validate and commit transactions upon reaching consensus. An Adaptive Batch Mechanism (ABM) is introduced to optimize block formation by dynamically adjusting batch parameters and using dummy transactions to maintain efficiency during low and varying transaction loads. Experimental validation using Hyperledger Fabric demonstrates the system's ability to enhance decentralized logging, reduce delays in transaction processing, and facilitate inter-domain coordination while maintaining robust security through a distributed trust model.

INDEX TERMS Batching, blockchain, DLT, SDN, trust.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN MODERN network environments, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has become a key technology for dynamically managing network infrastructure, particularly in heterogeneous systems where multiple network domains coexist. By decoupling the control plane from the data plane, SDN enables flexible and scalable management of diverse domains, each typically operating with its own SDN controller [1]. These controllers play a crucial role in overseeing network operations within their respective domains, ensuring that local configurations are maintained and adapted as network conditions evolve. While this decentralized approach to network management offers flexibility, it also presents significant challenges in maintaining consistency, trust, and

security across the domains. Ensuring that changes in one domain are accurately and securely reflected across others is critical to preventing misconfigurations and ensuring reliable network operations [2].

Traditionally, these challenges have been addressed through centralized mechanisms like Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) and Certificate Authorities (CAs), which provide trust through cryptographic certificates and identity verification [3], [4]. While these methods offer a level of security, they also introduce certain limitations, particularly when applied to highly decentralized and distributed environments. PKI-based systems often struggle with issues like single points of failure, limited scalability, and a lack of transparency, as trust is concentrated in a few centralized

entities. Additionally, the process of certificate issuance and revocation can be cumbersome, especially when dealing with cross-domain or multi-party collaboration [5], [6].

Recently, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) such as blockchain have emerged as promising alternatives for addressing the challenges of ensuring trust, security, and consistency in multi-domain SDN environments [7], [8]. Blockchain technology ensures that transactions are immutably recorded on a distributed ledger, eliminating the need for centralized authorities to validate and store information. With the ability to provide automatic, transparent verification of transactions and network operations, blockchain enhances both security and collaboration across multiple domains [9], [10]. This decentralized trust model also improves resilience by removing single points of failure and allowing all participants in the network to verify the state of the system independently [11].

In particular, permissioned blockchains have gained traction within multi-domain SDN environments because they provide the governance, access control, and compliance mechanisms needed to support cross-domain collaboration [12]. In these settings, where SDN controllers from different domains collaborate to manage network configurations, permissioned blockchains ensure that only authorized parties can record and verify changes, reducing the risk of misconfigurations or security vulnerabilities. Unlike public blockchains, which are open to all participants, permissioned blockchains combine decentralized trust with strict access control, allowing organizations to align blockchain operations with their specific policies and business logic [13].

Despite the benefits, blockchain technology introduces a new set of challenges, particularly related to performance and scalability [14]. One key bottleneck in blockchain-based systems arises from the grouping of transactions into blocks for commitment to the ledger. The handling of transaction batching varies across blockchain platforms. For instance, in some permissioned blockchains [15], blocks are created dynamically based on criteria such as transaction volume or total batch size, meaning blocks can be created as soon as the batching thresholds are met. However, when transaction volumes are low, this system may experience delays as it waits for the batch to fill before committing a block, leading to increased latency [16].

This paper proposes a transaction batching strategy tailored for SDN controllers in multi-domain environments, where each SDN controller also functions as a validator node on a permissioned blockchain. In the multi-domain SDN context, variable traffic rates across domains and the need for distributed trust introduce additional challenges. To address these issues, an Adaptive Batch Mechanism (ABM) is introduced, which dynamically adjusts batch parameters in real time minimizing latency during low-traffic periods while maximizing block utilization during bursts. Specifically, the proposed method combines adaptive timeouts, transaction padding, and periodic flushing to ensure that topology

management operations (such as adding, updating, and deleting network devices and links) are securely recorded and efficiently shared across domains.

The core novelty lies in the co-design of ABM with the trust model specific to multi-domain SDN. Unlike standalone batching optimisations, ABM integrates with decentralised controller logic, enabling trust coordination without changes to consensus protocols. By binding batch triggers to SDN operation events, the system ensures responsive, secure, and consistent transaction recording. The effectiveness of this mechanism is validated through extensive experimentation in Hyperledger Fabric, demonstrating improvements in latency reduction, operational efficiency, and robust inter-domain coordination under variable and low transaction rates.

This paper incorporates the following scientific contributions:

- An inter-domain strategy for distributed trust in multi-domain SDN environments, where SDN controllers act as validator nodes in a permissioned blockchain. This strategy distributes trust, eliminates the need for centralized authorities, and enhances security by allowing each controller to independently verify and commit transactions, ensuring consistency across domains.
- A dynamic batching mechanism that adjusts batch parameters in real time based on transaction volume conditions to optimize transaction throughput, block utilization, and reduce latency, particularly during low-volume transaction periods. This mechanism operates externally to the blockchain core and requires no changes to the underlying consensus or ledger processes.
- An adaptive timeout and transaction padding approach that addresses delays caused by low transaction volumes by ensuring efficient batch filling or padding before the timeout, reducing overall transaction latency.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II reviews the related work. Section III describes the system model and the specifics of the proposed mechanism. Section IV presents the experimental setup and performance evaluations. Section V discusses the security analysis of the distributed inter-domain trust. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The integration of DLT and SDN has emerged as a promising area for addressing the challenges of multi-domain network management, particularly in scenarios that demand decentralized trust, security and privacy. Recent surveys and reviews have explored various dimensions of this integration, offering insights into its potential while highlighting ongoing challenges.

A. INSIGHTS FROM LITERATURE SURVEYS

The authors in [17] highlight the need to decentralize the traditionally centralized SDN architecture, particularly in

Flying Ad-Hoc Networks. The study categorizes solutions such as multi-controller architectures and blockchain-based approaches, emphasizing DLT's role in enhancing trust and reliability. While the survey provides a thorough analysis of decentralization strategies, its applicability to inter-domain SDN management remains underexplored, presenting an opportunity to extend these frameworks to broader contexts. In a multi-stakeholder environment, blockchain's ability to enable secure and transparent orchestration is evident. The study in [18] proposes a permissioned blockchain architecture for managing the lifecycle of network services in multi-cloud and multi-domain setups. By ensuring trusted interactions between stakeholders such as Cloud Service Providers and Mobile Network Operators, the study aligns well with the challenges faced in SDN-driven inter-domain scenarios, validating blockchain's potential in such environments.

The application of blockchain to ensure security, privacy, and trust in 5G network slicing is discussed in [19]. The paper connects blockchain's decentralized ledger capabilities to the negotiation processes between stakeholders in multi-domain setups. By ensuring immutable and auditable transaction records, the blockchain addresses trust issues inherent to network slicing. The survey also identifies gaps in real-world implementations, calling for further research to validate blockchain's potential in operational multi-domain environments. Expanding on DLT applications for mobile networks, the analysis in [20] explores blockchain's role in cellular networks, focusing on inter-actor communication and cooperation. While primarily addressing the radio and core networks, the study provides a foundation for adapting these principles to SDN environments, where trust and secure coordination across domains are critical.

The analysis provided in [19] categorizes blockchain-based solutions, evaluating their ability to address critical threats such as integrity, authenticity, availability, trust, and privacy in SDN and network slicing environments. These are pivotal concerns in multi-domain networks, where the decentralization of trust and secure inter-domain operations are vital. However, the review also highlights significant challenges, particularly in achieving blockchain scalability. Blockchain systems operate within a well-documented trade-off triangle of decentralization, security, and scalability. Current implementations often optimize for only two aspects at the cost of the third. For instance, first-generation blockchains like Bitcoin and Ethereum suffer from low transaction throughput and small block sizes. As a fundamental technology for future networks, DLT must evolve to address this scalability bottleneck while maintaining decentralization and security. Novel architectures, such as sharding techniques, block size increases, and improved consensus algorithms, are currently under research to enhance the throughput and scalability of blockchain systems, presenting an essential area for future exploration.

Further emphasizing the potential of DLT and SDN integration, [8] offers an extensive overview of their combined

capabilities in addressing security and privacy challenges. By highlighting the complexities of multi-domain SDN environments, the survey proposes blockchain as a decentralized and immutable ledger for recording network transactions and configurations. While it identifies challenges like latency and the need for optimized consensus mechanisms, it also highlights opportunities for further exploration in real-world scenarios, especially focusing on scalability solutions that align with multi-domain SDN requirements.

Lastly, the study in [21] extends the discussion to Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) frameworks for 5G and beyond networks. The authors emphasize blockchain's benefits, such as decentralized trust, enhanced security, and automation through smart contracts. By establishing a permissioned blockchain network, ZSM frameworks can secure inter-domain operations, reducing risks associated with malicious actors. Despite these theoretical benefits, the study highlights the lack of practical implementations, urging further exploration of blockchain's performance in operational deployments.

B. RESEARCH FRAMEWORKS AND IMPLEMENTATIONS

Building upon the insights from surveys, specific frameworks and systems have been proposed to leverage blockchain for inter-domain SDN management.

The authors in [22] investigate the use of blockchain for managing responsibility and accountability within disaggregated optical networks. The proposed framework establishes a dependable and secure record of events and interactions across various levels within disaggregated network elements, including interactions among SDN controllers, between SDN controllers and network nodes, and within disaggregated network nodes themselves. It tackles critical challenges such as managing Service Level Agreements (SLA) and ensuring the quality of transmission in multi-vendor, multi-domain environments, showcasing the potential of blockchain in managing complex network architectures. Scalability and effectiveness are validated through a disaggregated network testbed. However, the study acknowledges challenges such as high implementation costs and resource demands. Additionally, there are no detailed specifications regarding the blockchain type and consensus mechanism, which could have a potential impact on the overall performance of the framework.

The authors in [23] and [24] explore blockchain's potential to enhance security and decentralization in advanced network management frameworks. In [23], the focus is on ZSM frameworks within multi-domain networks, highlighting blockchain's advantages over traditional databases, such as its decentralized and immutable nature, which provide enhanced security and trustworthiness. However, the study lacks implementation and performance evaluations, highlighting the need for real-world validations to assess blockchain's applicability fully. Complementing this, [24] proposes a blockchain-enabled framework for decentralized

network management in 6G mobile networks, emphasizing spectrum and infrastructure sharing while eliminating centralized authorities through cryptographic mechanisms. While promising, the framework primarily relies on simulations, leaving its practical integration with emerging 6G technologies as an open question for future research.

Reference [25] and [26] address trust, privacy, and scalability challenges in next-generation networks through complementary approaches. Reference [25] focuses on dynamic slice scaling in 5G multi-domain environments via the 5GZORRO platform, leveraging ETSI ZSM's closed-loop architecture, DLT for secure resource sharing, Kubernetes for orchestration, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for intent-driven management. It automates slice lifecycle management, including resource discovery, optimization, and scaling, as demonstrated in a Content Delivery Network (CDN) use case. Similarly, [26] proposes a privacy-aware architecture for managing the level of trust in 6G intent-based networks, combining service attestation, proofs of transit, and DLT for traceability. Privacy is preserved using homomorphic encryption and searchable encryption, with federated learning enabling decentralized orchestration. Both approaches highlight the potential of DLT and AI-driven automation; however, concerns about latency induced by DLT become more significant when coupled with the computational overhead of encryption and federated learning, which need careful consideration for high-demand real-world scenarios.

In [27], the authors propose a blockchain-based framework for secure routing in multidomain SDN-enabled Internet of Things (IoT) networks. By leveraging blockchain smart contracts for abstracted topology sharing and integrating a reputation mechanism, the framework ensures data integrity, mitigates black-hole attacks, and enhances routing reliability. Experimental results validate its effectiveness in reducing packet loss and improving resilience to malicious behaviour. Similarly, [28] introduces the Secure Interconnected Autonomous System Architecture (SIASA) for multidomain IoT ecosystems in Beyond 5G (B5G) networks. Combining SDN with a hierarchical blockchain federation, SIASA ensures secure inter-domain communication and facilitates scalable transactions via a blockchain-enabled SDN gateway. While a proof-of-concept evaluation demonstrates reduced latency and improved throughput in inter-blockchain operations, latency remains a concern, particularly for applications requiring real-time performance.

In [29] and [30], the authors propose DLT-based architectures for managing end-to-end (E2E) inter-domain transport network slices, emphasizing SLA monitoring and secure collaboration. Both approaches utilize the ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller [36], with one instance deployed per domain, and employ permissioned blockchains to facilitate inter-domain communication while maintaining operator privacy. The solutions enable abstracted topology sharing across domains and leverage blockchain to store and validate SLA-related data, ensuring traceability and mitigating SLA violations.

In [30], two blockchain integration models are proposed: the full permissioned distributed ledger (PDL), which centralizes interactions to enhance security and immutability at the cost of increased latency, and the complementary PDL, which reduces latency by selectively using blockchain for critical data while relying on peer-to-peer protocols for other communications. Experimental validation highlights the feasibility of these architectures, demonstrating their ability to dynamically reconfigure slices by excluding domains responsible for SLA breaches while balancing security, fault tolerance, and latency.

In [31], the authors present a blockchain-based architecture for connectivity provisioning across transport SDN domains, addressing single points of failure and enabling multi-operator compatibility. By integrating a PDL-transport manager module within each SDN controller, the framework uses blockchain for secure, transparent, and immutable collaboration, translating transactions into Open Network Foundation (ONF) Transport API (T-API) requests for configuring connectivity services. Validation on the ADRENALINE testbed [37] shows that E2E service deployment averages 4.08 seconds, with blockchain operations adding latency but enhancing security and fault tolerance, making it suitable for inter-domain SDN management.

In [32] and [33], the authors propose decentralized blockchain-based architectures for E2E Network Slice deployment across multi-domain networks. These approaches leverage Ethereum-based blockchains to replace centralized orchestrators, addressing single points of failure and fostering collaboration among domain owners. Both architectures utilize Network Slice Managers (NSM) or slicers and transport SDN controllers as blockchain peers to share resources while retaining operator independence securely. Blockchain ensures transparent, immutable interactions for managing slice requests and stitching network slice subnets across optical and packet-based transport domains. Despite enhancing security and fault tolerance, experimental results demonstrate that the blockchain introduces a time overhead for slice instantiation. Nevertheless, the decentralized architecture remains a viable solution for multi-domain network slicing scenarios.

In [34] and [35], the authors propose blockchain-based frameworks leveraging Hyperledger Fabric for secure and collaborative network management in multi-domain, multi-vendor environments. Both studies utilize DLT to enhance security, trust, and transparency by recording network topology changes and management transactions as immutable entries, ensuring data integrity and controlled access. In [34], the framework is validated using the ADRENALINE testbed, demonstrating manageable overhead with potential performance gains through optimized Hyperledger configurations. In [35], trust is distributed by treating SDN controllers as validator nodes using Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT) consensus [38], ensuring tamper-proof records and robust fault tolerance despite slight latency compared to RAFT consensus [39].

TABLE 1. Summary of the related work studies.

Research	Year	Description	Key Contribution	Limitation
[22]	2021	Blockchain framework for responsibility and accountability in disaggregated optical networks.	Dependable record for SLA management and QoS assurance; validated on a disaggregated testbed.	Performance/Latency
[23], [24]	2023, 2020	Enhancing security and decentralization in network management.	Blockchain-enabled ZSM frameworks and decentralized 6G management for spectrum sharing.	No test results for blockchain integration
[25]	2021	Dynamic slice scaling in 5G multi-domain networks via 5GZORRO.	Automation of slice lifecycle, secure resource sharing with DLT, and AI for orchestration.	Latency
[26]	2022	Privacy-aware architecture for LoT in 6G intent-based networks.	Service attestation, PoT for traffic path integrity, and privacy with HE and SE.	Overhead, Latency
[27]	2022	Blockchain-based secure routing in SDN-enabled IoT networks.	Abstracted topology sharing with smart contracts and reputation mechanisms.	Latency
[28]	2024	Secure IoT communication in B5G networks with hierarchical blockchain.	Scalable inter-domain transactions via SDN blockchain gateways.	Latency
[29], [30]	2022, 2023	SLA monitoring in multi-domain SDN with DLT.	ETSI TeraFlowSDN-enabled architectures with SLA data on permissioned blockchains.	Latency
[31]	2021	Blockchain-based connectivity provisioning in SDN domains.	Secure, transparent SDN domain interactions via ONF T-API and blockchain.	Latency
[32], [33]	2020, 2021	Decentralized E2E slice deployment in multi-domain networks.	Blockchain-enabled NSM for fault tolerance and immutable slice management.	Latency
[34], [35]	2024	Hyperledger-based frameworks for collaborative SDN management.	BFT consensus with tamper-proof records and performance optimization in multi-vendor setups.	Slight latency

A summary of the reviewed research is presented in Table 1, highlighting the contributions and limitations of each study.

C. DISCUSSION ON THE LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH GAPS

After analyzing the works presented in this literature review, it is evident that DLT, such as blockchain, offer significant benefits for multi-domain SDN environments. These benefits include enhanced security, transparency, and trust through decentralized management and tamper-proof recordkeeping. However, concerns about latency remain a critical challenge, particularly when scaling these solutions to accommodate high-throughput and real-time network operations.

This research builds upon the foundational advantage of DLT, which is distributing trust among stakeholders, as envisioned in [35], by treating each SDN controller in a multi-domain scenario as a validator in the blockchain network (illustrated in Fig. 1). This decentralized trust model enhances collaborative network management, ensures tamper-proof records, and reduces reliance on centralized authorities. To address the latency concerns inherent in blockchain operations, the proposed research introduces a dynamic batching mechanism that optimizes transaction processing by adjusting batch size and timing based on network load and transaction urgency. This approach maintains the security and trust benefits of DLT while reducing operational latency, providing an efficient solution for secure inter-domain collaboration.

While batching strategies have been studied in blockchain contexts, the work presented by the authors in [40] proposes a multi-batch scheduling technique designed for high-throughput, single-domain IoT environments. Their system employs a proxy-side scheduler to optimize transaction

flow into Hyperledger Fabric, improving delay metrics under synthetic loads. However, it does not address SDN integration or trust coordination across distributed domains. In contrast, our ABM operates natively within the SDN controller logic, adapting in real time to inter-domain events and validator configurations. It is built to work with permissioned blockchains where controllers act as consensus participants, enabling secure coordination across distributed administrative domains.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed system integrates SDN controllers across multiple domains, a blockchain-based inter-domain trust framework, and an adaptive batching mechanism to address key challenges in inter-domain communication. Fig. 2 illustrates the main components and their interactions: SDN controllers and multi-domain networks enabling distributed network control, inter-domain operations for network topology management, an ABM for optimizing blockchain transaction processing, and a blockchain network and ledger ensuring decentralized trust and efficient block utilization. The ABM is implemented within the application layer of each SDN controller. Together, these components provide a robust and secure framework for inter-domain network operations..

A. SDN CONTROLLERS AND MULTI-DOMAIN NETWORKS

In a multi-domain SDN environment like the one shown in Fig. 3, achieving network-wide coordination requires efficient inter-domain communication. Each SDN controller manages its local domain's topology, devices, and links while exchanging operational information with other domain

FIGURE 1. Blockchain integration for distributed trust in multi-domain SDN environments. Each SDN controller acts as a validator node within the blockchain network, effectively distributing trust across domains while maintaining tamper-proof records and ensuring collaborative network management [35].

controllers. This exchange is vital for maintaining a cohesive and seamless network operation across domains.

The proposed mechanism leverages blockchain technology to facilitate the secure exchange of information between SDN controllers. By immutably recording all inter-domain operations and ensuring validation through consensus, the blockchain serves as a decentralized trust anchor, addressing potential vulnerabilities that arise from malicious or misconfigured controllers.

In the proposed system, SDN controllers participate as validator nodes within the blockchain network. Logging SDN controller operations establishes a verifiable record of actions across the multi-domain environment, ensuring traceability. Trust is centered on the interactions between controllers, facilitated by their roles as validator nodes within the blockchain framework. This integration not only enhances accountability but also provides an immutable audit trail for network management operations, reinforcing the overall security and trustworthiness of the system.

B. INTER-DOMAIN OPERATIONS

Inter-domain operations involve managing the topology, links, and devices between SDN domains. These operations are crucial for maintaining synchronization and efficient communication across domains. Whenever an SDN

controller requires executing an inter-domain operation, it does so as a chaincode invocation on the blockchain.

In the proposed framework, inter-domain network operations rely on a JSON representation to manage and distinguish network elements. Fig. 4 presents this schema, which serves as the backbone for handling devices, links, and topologies, ensuring consistent representation and processing during blockchain transactions. A detailed description of the structure is provided below.

1) Device Representation: A device in the network is uniquely identified by a `device_id`, which contains a `device_uuid`. Several attributes characterize devices:

- `device_type`: Specifies the type of the device (e.g., router, switch).
- `device_drivers`: An array of integers representing the functionalities or drivers required for the device's operation.
- `device_config`: A configuration object containing:

- `config_rules`: A set of actions and custom configurations that define key-value pairs for device-specific settings.

2) Link Representation: A link is a connection between two network elements and is identified by a `link_id`,

FIGURE 2. Proposed model of a multi-domain SDN scenario with DLT integration and adaptive batch mechanism.

FIGURE 3. Multi-Domain SDN controllers distributed as validators in the blockchain.

which includes a link_uuid. Each link has the following properties:

- link_endpoint_ids: An array defining the endpoints of the link:
 - device_id: The unique identifier for the device at the endpoint.
 - endpointuuid: The unique identifier for the link’s endpoint within the device.

3) Topology Representation: A topology is a collection of devices and links, representing the overall network structure within a domain. The JSON schema defines a topology as:

- topology_id: A unique identifier for the topology, containing a topology_uuid.
- context_id: Links the topology to its broader context or network domain.

```

{
  "contexts": [{"context_id": {"context_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}}}],
  "topologies": [
    {"topology_id": {"context_id": {"context_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}},
      "topology_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}}}],
  "devices": [
    { "device_id": {"device_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}},
      "device_type": "string",
      "device_drivers": ["integer"],
      "device_config": {
        "config_rules": [
          {
            "action": "integer",
            "custom": {
              "resource_key": "string",
              "resource_value": "string or object"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ],
  "links": [
    { "link_id": {"link_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}},
      "link_endpoint_ids": [
        { "device_id": {"device_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}},
          "endpoint_uuid": {"uuid": "string"}
        ]
      }
    }
  ]
}
    
```

FIGURE 4. JSON schema representing network topologies, devices, and links.

1) CHAINCODE OPERATIONS

In the proposed framework, inter-domain network operations utilize chaincode functionality to ensure secure, immutable, and auditable record-keeping on the blockchain. The JSON

Algorithm 1 Workflow for Generating Unique Cross-Domain Identifiers

Input: *record_id*, a structured object with:

- domain_uuid*: The UUID of the domain,
- type*: The type of the record (e.g., *Device*, *Link*, *Topology*),
- record_uuid*: The UUID of the specific record.

Output: *hashKey*, a 64-character hexadecimal string representing the unique identifier.

- 1: **Input Fields:** Extract fields *domain_uuid*, *type*, and *record_uuid* from *record_id*.
- 2: **Construct JSON String:** Combine the fields into a JSON string:
 $jsonRecordId \leftarrow JSON.stringify(\{domain_uuid, type, record_uuid\})$.
- 3: **Initialize Hash Function:** Prepare the *SHA-256* hash function.
- 4: **Generate Hash:** Compute the hash value of the JSON string:
 $hashBytes \leftarrow SHA-256(jsonRecordId)$.
- 5: **Convert to Hexadecimal:** Transform the binary hash into a hexadecimal string:
 $hashKey \leftarrow ConvertToHex(hashBytes)$.
- 6: **Output Hash Key:** Return the unique *hashKey*.

schema, as previously described, defines the structure of network elements such as devices, links, and topologies. Each operation is uniquely identified by a *record_id*, which combines the domain context (*domain_uuid*), the type of the network element (*type*), and a specific identifier (*record_uuid*). This *record_id* is then hashed to create a unique key used in blockchain transactions, as shown in Algorithm 1.

When an SDN controller executes an inter-domain operation, the corresponding data is processed and stored on the blockchain through chaincode invocations. This mechanism not only enforces data integrity and consistency but also facilitates trust between network domains by leveraging the inherent properties of blockchain technology. The chaincode operations are detailed below:

- 1) **Store Record:** The *StoreRecord* operation adds a new record to the blockchain. The operation ensures the uniqueness of the record by creating a hash key derived from the *record_id*. If a record with the same key already exists, the operation is aborted. Upon successful storage, an event named *StoreRecord* is triggered, allowing SDN controllers to receive real-time notifications of the operation. This ensures that any new device, link, or topology added to the network is securely recorded and communicated across domains.
- 2) **Retrieve Record:** The *RetrieveRecord* operation allows SDN controllers to query the blockchain for specific records using the corresponding *record_id*. The operation generates a hash key and retrieves the data from the ledger.

If the record does not exist, the chaincode returns an error. This operation enables controllers to access the latest state of network elements, ensuring accurate and consistent data retrieval.

- 3) **Update Record:** The *UpdateRecord* operation modifies existing records in the blockchain. The operation verifies that the record exists using its hash key. If the record is found, it is updated with new data, and an *UpdateRecord* event is emitted. This operation is essential for scenarios where dynamic changes occur in network configurations, such as updates to device settings or modifications to link attributes.
- 4) **Delete Record:** The *DeleteRecord* operation marks a record as removed in the blockchain. Similar to the update operation, it first checks the existence of the record by generating its hash key. Upon successful deletion, a *DeleteRecord* event is triggered. This operation is particularly useful for decommissioning devices or links that are no longer part of the network topology.

While the *DeleteRecord* operation alters the record's information in the current state of the ledger, the previous state remains immutable and can still be audited within the blockchain. This ensures that the historical data is preserved across previous blocks, providing a complete and verifiable audit trail of all past operations.

Each chaincode operation is designed to emit events upon successful execution. These events, such as *StoreRecord*, *UpdateRecord*, and *DeleteRecord*, serve as real-time triggers for inter-domain communication and coordination. SDN controllers subscribed to these events can react to network changes promptly, ensuring synchronization across multiple domains.

A critical aspect of the proposed operations is the use of a cryptographic hashing mechanism to create unique keys for records as detailed on Algorithm 1. This mechanism defines a reusable and system-level coordination step that ensures globally unique identifiers across multiple SDN domains. It transforms the *record_id*, comprising the *domain_uuid*, *type*, and *record_uuid*, into a secure, fixed-size key used in all ledger operations. This ensures data integrity, prevents unauthorized modifications, and embeds the domain context within the identifier.

In a multi-domain blockchain environment, records from different domains coexist within the same ledger. By incorporating the *domain_uuid* into the hash key, the mechanism guarantees that each record is uniquely identifiable, even across domains. This design ensures that no two records, regardless of domain, share the same key, thereby maintaining data integrity and facilitating precise inter-domain operations.

C. ADAPTIVE BATCH MECHANISM

The ABM serves as the foundation of the proposed system, addressing performance and latency issues inherent in blockchain-based inter-domain operations. This mechanism is designed to optimize blockchain transaction processing by

FIGURE 5. Integration of the ABM within the SDN controller architecture. The ABM operates at the application layer, processing operations before submitting batched transactions to the blockchain.

grouping operations into batches before submission to the blockchain network. Fig. 5 shows how the ABM is integrated within the SDN controller architecture. This design allows the ABM to operate independently of SDN-specific southbound protocols (e.g., OpenFlow) and blockchain consensus mechanisms. Implemented at the application layer of the controller, it integrates seamlessly with the SDN control logic without interfering with packet forwarding, device configuration, or platform-specific blockchain internals.

Blockchain platforms rely on consensus mechanisms to validate transactions and create blocks. However, submitting transactions individually often results in underutilized blocks, which leads to inefficiencies and increased latency. While batching mechanisms might seem straightforward, the multi-domain SDN environment introduces additional challenges: traffic from multiple controllers can range from sporadic to bursty, and these controllers operate under a distributed trust model. The ABM addresses these challenges effectively. Specifically, when transaction rates are low, the mechanism prevents undue delays by lowering batch timeouts, and during high-traffic bursts, it ensures efficient block utilization that aligns with Hyperledger Fabric’s block-size and block-time constraints.

By grouping multiple inter-domain operations into a single batch, the mechanism leverages the blockchain’s capabilities more effectively, reducing latency while maintaining high throughput. This approach ensures that blocks are dispatched fully, improving transaction finality times.

1) MECHANISM DETAILS

The ABM operates through a structured workflow, as illustrated in Fig. 6. This workflow ensures efficient batch formation, timeout adjustments, and seamless blockchain dispatch. The steps are detailed below:

1) **Batch Formation:** Inter-domain operations initiated by SDN controllers are directed to the `addToBatch()` function. Transactions accumulate in the batch queue until one of the following conditions is met:

- The batch reaches the predefined size (`BATCH_SIZE`), indicating readiness for dispatch.
- The `currentTimeout` expires, prompting immediate processing to avoid unnecessary delays.

2) **Batch Processing Loop:** The **Batch Processing Loop** monitors the batch queue and triggers processing based on the following conditions:

- If the batch size meets or exceeds `BATCH_SIZE`, the loop invokes `processBatch()` to send transactions to the blockchain.
- If the timeout surpasses the `FLUSH_INTERVAL`, the mechanism evaluates the need for immediate processing or the inclusion of dummy transactions via `checkAndFlushBatch()`.

3) **Flush Interval:** The `FLUSH_INTERVAL` ensures timely batch processing in scenarios with sporadic transaction arrivals. This mechanism prevents excessive delays, ensuring that low-volume transactions are processed promptly without idling the system. Its behavior is as follows:

- The interval resets every time a transaction is added to the batch queue, creating a rolling timer that adapts to transaction patterns.
- If no new transactions arrive within the flush interval, it triggers batch processing even if the batch size is below `BATCH_SIZE`.

The flush interval can be expressed as in (1):

$$F(t) = \begin{cases} F_{\text{init}} & \text{if } t = t_0, \\ F(t_{n-1}) + \Delta t & \text{if transaction arrives at } t_n, \\ 0 & \text{if } t - t_{n-1} \geq F_{\text{interval}}, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where:

$F(t)$: Current flush timer at time t ,

F_{init} : Initial `FLUSH_INTERVAL` value when the timer starts,

$F(t_{n-1})$: Flush timer value from the last transaction at t_{n-1} ,

Δt : Elapsed time since the last transaction,

F_{interval} : Maximum duration allowed before triggering a flush,

t_n : Time of the n -th transaction,

t_{n-1} : Time of the $(n - 1)$ -th transaction.

4) **Adaptive Timeout:** The timeout dynamically adjusts based on transaction arrival rates:

- **High Traffic:** During high transaction rates, batches fill quickly, making the timeout less critical. The timeout is always equal to `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT`, as batches are processed when full.
- **Low Traffic:** During low transaction rates, the timeout decreases incrementally by the `FLUSH_INTERVAL` until reaching `MIN_TIMEOUT`. This avoids extended delays for individual transactions in underfilled batches.

The adaptive timeout mechanism is expressed mathematically:

$$T_{n+1} = \begin{cases} T_{\text{default}}, & \text{if } S \geq S_{\text{batch}}, \\ \max(T_{\text{min}}, T_n - \Delta T), & \text{if } S < S_{\text{batch}}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 6. Workflow of the dynamic batching mechanism, illustrating transaction accumulation, adaptive timeout adjustment, batch processing, and the use of dummy transactions for efficient block utilization and reduced latency.

where:

- T_n : Timeout value for the n -th batch processing loop,
- T_{default} : The DEFAULT_TIMEOUT value,
- T_{min} : The MIN_TIMEOUT value,
- ΔT : Incremental timeout reduction step by FLUSH_INTERVAL,
- S : Number of transactions in the batch queue,
- S_{batch} : Threshold BATCH_SIZE for processing.

5) Dummy Transactions: To ensure efficient block utilization, dummy transactions are appended to the batch when the timeout expires before the batch reaches BATCH_SIZE. These placeholders prevent the creation of underfilled blocks, which can compromise blockchain performance.

The logic behind dummy transactions can be expressed as follows:

$$T_{\text{batch}} = \begin{cases} T_{\text{real}} + T_{\text{dummy}}, & \text{if } |T_{\text{real}}| < \text{BATCH_SIZE}, \\ T_{\text{real}}, & \text{if } |T_{\text{real}}| \geq \text{BATCH_SIZE}. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where:

- T_{batch} : Final set of transactions to be dispatched,
- T_{real} : Set of real transactions in the batch at the time of processing,
- T_{dummy} : Set of dummy transactions added to reach BATCH_SIZE,
- $|T_{\text{real}}|$: Cardinality of the set of real transactions,
- BATCH_SIZE: Predefined size of a full batch.

The dummy transactions are dynamically generated as placeholders, as represented in (4), where T_{dummy} represents a single dummy transaction, ChaincodeInvoke denotes the invocation of a chaincode function, DUMMY_FUNCTION is a predefined chaincode function that performs no meaningful operation, and \emptyset indicates an empty set of arguments passed to the function. Their inclusion ensures:

- 1) *Consistent Block Size*: Each block achieves the predefined size, maximizing blockchain throughput.
- 2) *Timely Block Formation*: Blocks are dispatched promptly without waiting indefinitely for new transactions.
- 3) *Blockchain Integrity*: Even though dummy transactions do not carry real data, they maintain the operational consistency of the blockchain, avoiding irregular block intervals.
- 4) *Efficient*: Adds minimal processing overhead to maintain block consistency.
- 5) *Transparent*: Can be identified as a dummy transaction in logs and events.

$$T_{\text{dummy}} = \text{ChaincodeInvoke}(\text{DUMMY_FUNCTION}, \emptyset) \quad (4)$$

Importantly, dummy transactions are not persistent overhead. Their inclusion is tied to traffic sparsity: when the transaction rate stabilises and consistently exceeds the BATCH_SIZE per time unit, the batch naturally fills with real transactions, and dummy transactions are no longer triggered. This self-suppressing behaviour ensures that the system converges to optimal batching performance under sustained traffic, while only incurring minimal overhead during transient low-load periods.

6) *Blockchain Dispatch*: Once the batch is finalized, the $\text{processBatch}()$ function organizes the transactions into the appropriate format and submits them for further processing through interaction with the chaincode, ensuring the transactions are executed and committed to the blockchain. All transactions in the batch are processed collectively, optimizing the efficiency of the operation. The mechanism also ensures that even incomplete batches are padded with dummy transactions to meet predefined batch size requirements, maintaining consistent operational flow.

D. BLOCKCHAIN NETWORK AND LEDGER

The proposed system utilizes a permissioned blockchain network, with SDN controllers serving as validator nodes, as shown in Fig. 7. This architecture embeds the controllers directly into the consensus process, enabling them to verify inter-domain operations independently. By distributing validation responsibilities across multiple domains, the system establishes a decentralized trust model. This approach eliminates reliance on a central authority, significantly enhancing the security, reliability, and resilience of inter-domain communications.

FIGURE 7. A representation of multi-domain SDN controllers acting as validator nodes within a blockchain network. Each SDN controller is embedded in the consensus mechanism, independently validating transactions and ensuring secure interdomain collaboration.

1) BLOCKCHAIN NETWORK

In this permissioned blockchain setup, SDN controllers, acting as validator nodes, are integral to the consensus mechanism. Each controller independently validates proposed operations, both from its domain and those originating from other domains. This process ensures robust decision-making by requiring a majority agreement among validator nodes, typically needing $2f + 1$ endorsements (where f represents the maximum number of tolerable faulty nodes) to achieve consensus. The validation process, detailed in Algorithm 2, illustrates how SDN controllers coordinate to validate and commit transactions using established BFT consensus mechanisms.

The coordination process implemented by Algorithm 2 involves the following steps:

- 1) *Transaction Proposal*: Each validator node executes the chaincode for the proposed SDN operation to verify its correctness and compliance with local policy rules and network state.
- 2) *Endorsement Collection*: Validator nodes independently evaluate the transaction and provide endorsements if the chaincode execution aligns with the expected state. These endorsements are then collected for further evaluation.
- 3) *Consistency Check*: Once the endorsements meet the majority threshold of $2f + 1$ votes (where f is the maximum number of tolerable faulty nodes), a consistency check is performed. The consistency is determined by comparing the resulting hash of the operation, which should be identical across all valid endorsements. This step ensures uniformity and prevents discrepancies that could arise from malicious or faulty nodes.
- 4) *Transaction Commitment*: If the consistency check is successful, the transaction is committed to the ledger by all participating nodes. This step ensures that only validated inter-domain SDN actions are recorded, supporting a decentralised yet consistent trust framework across domains.

Algorithm 2 Workflow for Coordinated Consensus Using SDN Validator Nodes

Require: Record R , ValidatorNodes V , AllNodes P

Ensure: Consensus reached for Record R

```

    ▷ Step 1: Transaction Proposal and Validation
1: votes ← 0
2: vEndorsements ← {}
    ▷ Step 2: Endorsement Collection
3: for each node ∈ V do
4:   verified ← node.vChaincode(R)
5:   if verified then
6:     votes ← votes + 1
7:     vEndorsements ← vEndorsements ∪ {node}
8:   end if
9: end for
    ▷ Step 3: Consensus Evaluation
10: if votes ≥ 2f + 1 then
11:   consistent ← checkConsistency(vEndorsements)
12:   if consistent then
13:     for each node ∈ P do
14:       node.CommitState(R)
15:     end for
16:     return "Success: Consensus achieved, record committed"
17:   else
18:     return "Error: Inconsistent endorsements detected"
19:   end if
20: else
21:   return "Error: Consensus not reached"
22: end if

```

Note:

$vChaincode()$ validates the record through chaincode execution.
 $checkConsistency()$ ensures all valid endorsements have consistent results.
 $CommitState()$ commits the record to the ledger after consensus.

This systematic process guarantees that only valid and consistent operations are recorded on the blockchain, reinforcing its reliability and trustworthiness. Algorithm 2 formalises the coordination logic used to apply established BFT-style validation in a multi-domain SDN environment. Each endorsement is recorded, and the final decision to commit a transaction is based on collective agreement, thereby eliminating the need for a central authority.

1) Block Formation in the Blockchain: The block formation process in the permissioned blockchain is governed by two parameters: the $BLOCK_SIZE$ and the $BLOCK_WINDOW$. A block is formed either when the number of transactions reaches the predefined block size or when the block timeout expires. To optimize transaction processing, the system

FIGURE 8. Block formation with the default blockchain mechanism. At high transaction volumes, blocks are dispatched instantly upon reaching $BLOCK_SIZE$. At low transaction volumes, blocks are delayed until the $BLOCK_WINDOW$ expires.

FIGURE 9. Block formation with the dynamic batching mechanism. Regardless of transaction volume, the $BATCH_SIZE$ matches the $BLOCK_SIZE$, and the adaptive timeout ensures prompt block dispatch regardless of the $BLOCK_WINDOW$.

prioritizes responsiveness by dispatching blocks immediately once they are filled, even if the block timeout has not elapsed. This approach ensures that high transaction volumes are processed without unnecessary delays, maintaining the blockchain’s efficiency.

However, in scenarios with low transaction volumes, block formation is primarily governed by the $BLOCK_WINDOW$. This can result in increased latency as the system waits for the timeout to expire before dispatching the block, as illustrated in Fig. 8. This mechanism is characteristic of permissioned blockchain platforms such as Hyperledger Fabric.

To address this challenge, the proposed batching mechanism aligns with the blockchain’s parameters by setting the $BATCH_SIZE$ equal to the $BLOCK_SIZE$ and the $DEFAULT_TIMEOUT$ equal to the $BLOCK_WINDOW$. As described in (2), the adaptive timeout starts at $DEFAULT_TIMEOUT$ and dynamically adjusts based on operation arrival rates, ensuring that the $FLUSH_INTERVAL$ or the adaptive timeout is always less than the $BLOCK_WINDOW$. Fig. 9 illustrates the effect of the dynamic batching mechanism. Regardless of the transaction volume, the block is always filled and dispatched promptly. This ensures that transactions are processed in a timely manner, avoiding the delays inherent in the default mechanism.

By dynamically adjusting the batching process, the proposed mechanism accelerates block formation, allowing transactions to be processed promptly without relying on

the full block timeout, even in low transaction volume scenarios.

2) BLOCKCHAIN LEDGER

The Blockchain Ledger serves as an immutable repository for recording all inter-domain operations. Each block added to the ledger is cryptographically linked to the previous one, creating a tamper-proof chain of records. This ensures that any audits or disputes can rely on a verifiable and transparent history of operations. The ledger’s design supports high availability, as only verified participants in the blockchain network have access to its contents, ensuring trust and traceability.

To maintain consistency, every participant in the blockchain network—each SDN controller acting as a validator node—produces batches that align with the `BLOCK_SIZE`. This coordination ensures that the batching mechanism does not disrupt the consensus process or the ledger’s integrity. Furthermore, the use of hashed unique identifiers `UNIQUE_ID` for each transaction enhances consistency across the distributed system by preventing duplication and enabling efficient verification.

The event-driven nature of the system further strengthens the ledger’s functionality. Each successfully validated transaction triggers an event, ensuring real-time updates and seamless synchronization between participating SDN controllers. These events notify controllers of completed operations, maintaining a consistent and coherent state across the network. Algorithm 3 demonstrates the generalized chaincode operations, showcasing how the hashing mechanism generates a unique key for every transaction and how events are triggered upon successful execution.

Algorithm 3 implements standard read and write operations found in permissioned blockchains, but its significance lies in how it orchestrates inter-domain coordination within the proposed SDN framework. By enforcing a consistent structure for ledger operations (add, update, delete) and tightly integrating real-time event emission, the algorithm enables SDN controllers to maintain a synchronised and auditable view of network activity. This event-driven structure transforms the blockchain from a passive ledger into an active coordination layer, supporting responsive and decentralised network management without relying on external messaging systems.

The ledger’s efficiency is closely tied to the ABM, which ensures that blocks are effectively fully utilized by batching transactions. This integration ensures that the blockchain operates at peak performance, even under varying transaction volumes, while maintaining the robustness required for inter-domain trust and communication.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND PERFORMANCE RESULTS

A. DEPLOYMENT SETUP

The experimental setup is depicted in Fig. 10. The deployment leverages a permissioned blockchain based on Hyperledger Fabric (HLF) version 2.5+, configured with a

Algorithm 3 Generalized Chaincode-Based Inter-Domain SDN Operations

Input:

operationType: Type of operation (*add*, *update*, *delete*),
record_id: Structured object containing *domainUuid*,
type, and *recordUuid*,
dataJson: Data for the record (required for *add* and *update*).

Output: Result of the operation.

```

1: Generate           Key:           hashKey           ←
   GenerateRecordHashKey(record_id).
2: Check             Existence:         exists           ←
   CheckIfRecordExists(hashKey).
3: if operationType = “add” and exists then
4:   Abort: Return Error(“Record already exists”).
5: else if operationType = “update” and not exists then
6:   Abort: Return Error(“Record does not exist”).
7: else if operationType = “delete” and not exists then
8:   Abort: Return Error(“Record does not exist”).
9: end if
10: Execute Operation:
    • add: PutState(hashKey, dataJson),
    • update: PutState(hashKey, dataJson),
    • delete: DelState(hashKey).
11: Trigger Event: SetEvent(operationType, record_id,
   dataJson).
12: Return Success: Return “Operation Successful”.

```

TABLE 2. Adaptive timeout parameters.

Parameter	Value
BATCH_SIZE	10 operations (matches <code>BLOCK_SIZE</code>)
DEFAULT_TIMEOUT	2 seconds (matches <code>BLOCK_WINDOW</code>)
MIN_TIMEOUT	500 milliseconds (ensures responsiveness during low traffic)
FLUSH_INTERVAL	100 milliseconds (triggers timely flushing during sporadic transactions)

`BLOCK_SIZE` of 10 transactions and a `BLOCK_WINDOW` of 2 seconds. These parameters govern block formation: a block is formed either when the number of transactions reaches `BLOCK_SIZE` or when the `BLOCK_WINDOW` expires. If a block reaches its capacity before the timeout elapses, it is dispatched immediately.

The system incorporates the ABM, whose parameters are outlined in Table 2. The `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT` is aligned with the `BLOCK_WINDOW`, ensuring synchronization with the blockchain’s native configuration. The `MIN_TIMEOUT` is set to 500 milliseconds, enabling the ABM to maintain responsiveness under low transaction volumes. The `FLUSH_INTERVAL`, set to 100 milliseconds, prevents prolonged delays in processing sporadic transactions by triggering timely batch dispatches. The initial values for `MIN_TIMEOUT` and `FLUSH_INTERVAL` were chosen

FIGURE 10. System deployment across four nodes, each hosting a peer for transaction endorsement and an orderer for block formation. Nodes are connected through a shared channel, ensuring secure, fault-tolerant, and decentralized interdomain operations.

based on empirical observations of typical SDN scenarios. Section IV-C illustrates how varying these parameters affects latency and throughput, enabling operators to fine-tune them for specific traffic patterns and operational requirements. These configurations ensure that the ABM optimally complements the blockchain’s default mechanisms, thereby improving performance across varying transaction rates.

The blockchain network is distributed across four Linux machines, each representing an independent organization configured to emulate different network domains. These organizations are connected through a common channel, which facilitates inter-domain communication by enabling all organizations to write and read data from the blockchain. Each machine hosts:

- *One peer node:* Responsible for endorsing transactions and executing smart contracts (chaincode).
- *One orderer node:* Participating in the consensus mechanism for block formation.

To ensure robust trust distribution and resilience against potential malicious or faulty nodes, the default consensus mechanism of HLF (RAFT) was replaced with BFT. The endorsement policy was modified to require endorsements from at least $2f + 1$ nodes for each transaction. While this approach mitigates the risks posed by faulty nodes by ensuring redundancy in endorsements, it also leverages trust by providing multiple independent validations.

The SDN controller used in this study is the *TeraFlowSDN controller*, an open-source, microservice-based, cloud-native, and carrier-grade SDN management platform. It has been

integrated with a **DLT component** to interact with the blockchain. As part of the cloud-native architecture of TeraFlowSDN, the DLT component is deployed as a container within its Kubernetes-based deployment. This integration facilitates seamless interaction with the blockchain while adhering to the scalability and resilience principles of TeraFlowSDN’s design.

The ABM is implemented within the DLT component. The ABM aggregates inter-domain operations into batches, ensuring that transactions are efficiently submitted to the blockchain. Inter-domain operations such as STORE, UPDATE, DELETE, and FETCH are processed through the DLT component. Operations that modify the blockchain state (STORE, UPDATE, and DELETE) are first handled by the ABM, which optimizes block utilization by batching them for efficient processing during low transaction volumes. These batched operations are then executed as chaincode operations on the blockchain. Conversely, operations such as FETCH, which do not modify the blockchain state, are directly executed without passing through the ABM. Although the current implementation is deployed on Hyperledger Fabric, the ABM operates independently of blockchain-specific internals. This design allows ABM to be portable across permissioned blockchain platforms that support basic transaction submission and block dispatch via size or timeout thresholds

The chaincode, coded in Golang, is installed and activated on all peer nodes in the HLF network. This deployment ensures that all peers are capable of endorsing transactions and executing chaincode operations, maintaining consistency and reliability across the blockchain network.

To facilitate monitoring and validation, a **block explorer** is deployed [41]. This explorer, equipped with appropriate identities, provides insights into block creation, block size, block contents, and transaction execution. These insights are crucial for analyzing and interpreting the results presented in this paper, offering detailed visibility into the blockchain’s operations and supporting the evaluation of the proposed mechanism.

B. PERFORMANCE TESTS

For testing purposes, the DLT component of TeraFlowSDN has been replicated and distributed across four Docker containers, each interacting directly with a specific peer node in the blockchain network. This setup mirrors a realistic deployment scenario, reflecting how cloud-native SDN controllers would interact with permissioned blockchains in production environments. It leverages the microservice-based architecture of TeraFlowSDN to ensure scalability and modularity. By replicating the DLT component across distributed nodes, the deployment not only supports diverse testing conditions but also validates the design under practical, inter-domain operational constraints. Together with their corresponding peer and orderer nodes, these instances form a representative model of the proposed distributed trust framework.

The experiments execute inter-domain operations under various transaction rates to evaluate the performance benefits of the ABM. **JSON files** containing network topology information are used as the test dataset. Three distinct test scenarios are conducted:

- *Scenario 1: incremental high transaction rates*
- *Scenario 2: incremental low transaction rates*
- *Scenario 3: concurrent stress test*

For each scenario, the system's performance is evaluated with and without the ABM. The performance metrics are computed as the maximum time taken to process the first transaction T_{first} of a batch (in the case of ABM) or a block (in the no-ABM setup) for each TPS rate. This represents the worst-case scenario, as it includes the time required for the batch or block to form, the consensus process, and the final commit to the ledger. Each test runs for 5 minutes to ensure reliable and consistent evaluation of performance under sustained conditions.

The **scenario 1** evaluates the system's performance under transaction rates ranging from 1 TPS to 100 TPS. The **scenario 2** focuses on the benefits of the ABM under lower transaction volumes, ranging from 1 TPS to 10 TPS.

Scenario 3 evaluates the system's ability to handle high transaction rates under continuous load. During this test, operations are executed at varying TPS rates: 1 TPS, 5 TPS, 50 TPS, and 100 TPS. These operations are performed in parallel across four distributed DLT components, each interacting directly with its corresponding blockchain peer node. This setup emulates a scenario where multiple controllers simultaneously interact with the blockchain. The maximum time to process the first transaction of a batch or block (T_{first}) is calculated as an average across the four DLT components for each target rate. The results are compared between setups with and without the ABM, providing insights into the system's performance under concurrent operations.

1) RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results for Scenario 1, evaluating transaction rates from 1 to 100 TPS, are shown in Fig. 11. At lower rates (e.g., 1 TPS), the ABM efficiently dispatches batches using the `FLUSH_INTERVAL`, significantly reducing delays caused by reliance on the `BLOCK_WINDOW` in the no-ABM configuration. This demonstrates that the ABM provides substantial benefits in scenarios where the transaction rate is insufficient to fill a block within the `BLOCK_WINDOW` interval. As the transaction rate reaches 10 TPS, blocks begin to be processed based on the `BLOCK_SIZE/BATCH_SIZE`, regardless of whether the ABM is utilized. Beyond 80 TPS, the latency in both configurations stabilizes as transactions are processed and dispatched consistently, reflecting the system's maximum throughput capacity.

Scenario 2, depicted in Fig. 12, focuses on transaction rates from 1 to 10 TPS. These results highlight the benefits of the ABM in handling low to moderate transaction rates. At 1 TPS, the ABM leverages the `FLUSH_INTERVAL` to dispatch

FIGURE 11. Maximum latency comparison for processing the first transaction (T_{first}) in Scenario 1: High transaction rates (1 TPS to 100 TPS) with and without ABM, showcasing stabilization at higher rates.

FIGURE 12. Maximum latency comparison for processing the first transaction (T_{first}) in Scenario 2: Low to medium transaction rates (1 TPS to 10 TPS) with and without ABM.

underfilled blocks promptly, avoiding the delays associated with the `BLOCK_WINDOW` in the no-ABM configuration. For scenarios with low or sporadic transaction rates, the ABM demonstrates a clear advantage in latency, even when considering the maximum latency of T_{first} for processing the first transaction of a batch or block. At 10 TPS, both configurations converge as the transaction rate matches the `BLOCK_SIZE/BATCH_SIZE`, leading to consistent block formation and minimal latency differences.

The concurrent stress test for scenario 3, depicted in Fig. 13, evaluates the system's performance under sustained transaction rates of 1 TPS, 5 TPS, 50 TPS, and 100 TPS. The results highlight a significant benefit of the ABM at lower rates, particularly at 1 TPS, where the dynamic batching mechanism effectively reduces delays caused by the `BLOCK_WINDOW`. A moderate benefit is also observed at 5 TPS, further demonstrating the ABM's ability to optimize block utilization under varying transaction volumes.

At higher rates (50 TPS and 100 TPS), the results for both configurations (with and without ABM) converge. This is because the constant arrival of transactions ensures that blocks are filled and dispatched immediately, even without the ABM. Consequently, the ABM does not provide too much improvement in these high-throughput scenarios.

FIGURE 13. Comparison of maximum latency for processing the first transaction (T_{first}) under stress test conditions for various TPS rates with and without ABM.

FIGURE 15. Block size comparison for varying transaction rates (1 TPS to 10 TPS) with and without ABM during Scenario 2.

FIGURE 14. Number of blocks generated for Scenario 2 under different transaction volumes with and without ABM. Each TPS step is running for a period of 5 minutes.

Fig. 14 shows the number of blocks generated in Scenario 2. Without the ABM, the blockchain relies entirely on the BLOCK_WINDOW to dispatch blocks when the BLOCK_SIZE is not reached. Low transaction rates (1 TPS and 5 TPS) result in fewer blocks being generated, as transactions accumulate slowly and require a full timeout period before dispatch. Consequently, the system suffers from increased delays in transaction processing. As the transaction rate increases, the number of blocks generated increases because the natural arrival rate of transactions aligns more closely with the BLOCK_SIZE.

In contrast, with the ABM, blocks are consistently dispatched at shorter intervals during low transaction rates (1 to 9 TPS) due to the FLUSH_TIMER, which in this case is set to 100ms. Since transactions arrive at a slower pace, incomplete batches are promptly dispatched to the blockchain, ensuring faster commitment and reducing delays. At higher transaction rates (10 TPS and beyond), the number of blocks generated becomes practically identical between the ABM and no-ABM configurations. This occurs because the transaction arrival rate matches or exceeds the block size (BLOCK_SIZE), naturally aligning the block generation patterns in both implementations.

Fig. 15 illustrates the block sizes observed across various transaction rates (1 TPS to 10 TPS) for both configurations.

Without the ABM, the block size varies significantly, particularly at low transaction rates (1 TPS to 4 TPS). This variability is caused by the reliance on the BLOCK_WINDOW, which dispatches blocks with fewer transactions when the block is not filled, resulting in increased transaction latency.

In contrast, with the ABM, the block size is consistently maintained at the maximum BLOCK_SIZE of 10 transactions, regardless of the transaction rate. This consistency is achieved by dynamically adjusting the batch timeout and padding incomplete batches with dummy transactions when necessary. Consequently, the ABM ensures uniform block sizes, mitigating the variability observed in the no-ABM configuration. As the transaction rate increases from 5 TPS to 10 TPS, both configurations begin to generate blocks that align more closely with the maximum BLOCK_SIZE.

2) DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The ABM reduces latency, particularly in scenarios with low or sporadic transaction rates. As observed in Scenario 1 (Fig. 11) and Scenario 2 (Fig. 12), the ABM utilizes the FLUSH_INTERVAL to dispatch underfilled blocks promptly, ensuring that transactions are committed to the blockchain without relying solely on the BLOCK_WINDOW. This dynamic adjustment mechanism prevents the prolonged delays experienced in the no-ABM configuration, where transactions must wait for either the block size to fill or the timeout to elapse. Consequently, the ABM accelerates operations, reducing the overall processing time and ensuring a faster response to network demands.

The ABM effectively addresses latency challenges in blockchain-based systems but introduces a trade-off in the form of an increased number of blocks generated, as shown in Fig. 14. At low transaction rates (e.g., 1 TPS to 5 TPS), the ABM frequently dispatches blocks filled with dummy transactions to maintain low latency. Although this increases the number of blocks, it ensures that transactions are not left waiting for the full BLOCK_WINDOW. For transaction rates exceeding the BLOCK_SIZE, the block generation patterns of the ABM and the no-ABM configurations converge, mitigating this trade-off.

FIGURE 16. Average transaction processing time for varying TPS under the prepared traffic pattern. The ABM consistently reduces latency compared to the no-ABM scenario, even under highly variable TPS conditions.

TABLE 3. Impact of dummy transactions on block utilization.

Transaction Rate (TPS)	Dummy Transactions per Block	Total Dummy Data (KB)
1	9	13.5
4	6	9
10	0	0

The ABM utilizes dummy transactions to fill incomplete batches, ensuring that the `BLOCK_SIZE` requirements are consistently met. In this deployment, a typical dummy transaction has a size of approximately 1.5 KB. Table 3 provides an analysis of the impact of dummy transactions on block utilization. While these transactions increase the total data transmitted on the blockchain, the resulting reduction in latency justifies the trade-off. Their inclusion ensures that transactions are processed promptly, avoiding prolonged delays caused by underfilled blocks. Moreover, their transparent identification within the ledger ensures that the blockchain’s integrity and functionality remain uncompromised.

In high transaction rate scenarios, the use of dummy transactions diminishes naturally as the increased transaction volume allows blocks to fill up without additional padding.

In real-world scenarios, where transaction rates are often variable and sporadic, the benefits of the ABM become even more pronounced. Unlike the controlled conditions established in this study, real-world systems encounter fluctuating traffic patterns and uneven transaction arrival rates. The ABM’s ability to dynamically adjust batching and dispatch intervals ensures that transactions are processed promptly, even during traffic spikes or periods of low activity. By minimizing delays and maintaining consistent performance across diverse conditions, the ABM provides a significant advantage in practical deployments.

To demonstrate the benefits of the ABM, a variable TPS scenario was prepared using a traffic pattern consisting of fluctuating TPS rates over a total of 82 steps. Each step represents a specific duration during which the TPS remains constant before transitioning to a new value. The TPS rates in this pattern vary dynamically between 1 TPS and 50 TPS, emulating the variability of real-world transaction patterns. This variation was designed to represent fluctuating network traffic conditions that may arise due to bursts of activity or idle periods in practical deployments. The TPS values were chosen to include rates below and above the `BLOCK_SIZE` (e.g., 10 transactions) to evaluate the system’s ability to handle underfilled and filled blocks.

The results, as shown in Fig. 16, present the average time taken to process transactions under this variable traffic pattern. This figure illustrates the clear advantages of the ABM in reducing latency and ensuring steady performance across all steps, regardless of the abrupt changes in TPS. The no-ABM scenario, in contrast, exhibits significant variability in processing times, particularly when the TPS falls below the `BLOCK_SIZE`, leading to delays caused by reliance on the `BLOCK_WINDOW` timeout. An interesting finding is that when the TPS aligns with multiples of the `BLOCK_SIZE` (e.g., 10 transactions), the no-ABM scenario can temporarily match the performance of the ABM due to the uniform filling of the block. However, significant variation in processing times remains evident in the no-ABM case.

Additionally, Fig. 17 illustrates the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of transaction processing times for both scenarios. Unlike the average results in Fig. 16, the CDF considers each individual transaction time for the variable TPS test. Up to the intersection point at 149.00 ms (marked by the dotted red line), both scenarios show similar performance, with a comparable fraction of transactions processed within that time. However, beyond the dotted

line, the “With ABM” curve rises sharply, indicating less variability and shorter delays. In contrast, the “Without ABM” curve flattens, indicating higher variability and longer delays for a significant portion of transactions.

C. PARAMETER SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

In this section, the chosen parameter values are justified by examining how different configurations affect transaction performance. All experiments rely on the prepared traffic pattern from Fig. 16 and Fig. 17, which includes bursts, idle periods, and variable arrival rates, approximating real-world multi-domain SDN scenarios. The parameters BATCH_SIZE, FLUSH_INTERVAL, MIN_TIMEOUT, and DEFAULT_TIMEOUT are varied to measure both the mean transaction time (with error bars representing the standard deviation) and, in specific cases, the number of blocks generated. Monitoring block generation ensures that parameter values do not excessively inflate the number of blocks, thus preserving an optimal balance between performance and overhead.

1) EFFECT OF BATCH_SIZE

Fig. 18 presents the mean transaction time (in milliseconds) as a function of BATCH_SIZE, which ranges from 1 to 30. The horizontal axis indicates different BATCH_SIZE configurations (an integer count of transactions per batch), while the bars represent average latency in milliseconds, and the error bars denote the corresponding standard deviation. Very small values of BATCH_SIZE (1–2) often process transactions individually, leading to higher latency and substantial variability. As the BATCH_SIZE increases (3–9), the average latency decreases, although the variation remains considerable. Around BATCH_SIZE = 10, the average latency reaches a minimal level with lower standard deviation, suggesting a favorable setting for the traffic pattern under study. Beyond this point (i.e., BATCH_SIZE > 10), overall delay can increase again because the system waits longer to accumulate larger batches. Consequently, a BATCH_SIZE of 10 is adopted in all experiments.

2) EFFECT OF FLUSH_INTERVAL

Fig. 19 shows how the mean transaction time and corresponding error bars vary with FLUSH_INTERVAL values ranging from 50 ms to 500 ms under the prepared traffic pattern. Lower intervals (50–100 ms) cause underfilled batches to be flushed more frequently, preventing prolonged waits for sporadic transactions and slightly reducing overall latency. At higher intervals (300–500 ms), latency remains relatively stable but may increase somewhat if the system waits excessively for incoming transactions. A FLUSH_INTERVAL of 100 ms appears to provide a balance between rapidly dispatching partial batches and avoiding undue overhead which causes variability of results from excessive flushing.

FIGURE 17. CDF of transaction processing times under the variable TPS scenario. The ABM shows a more consistent and predictable transaction processing time with less variability compared to the no-ABM case.

FIGURE 18. Mean and standard deviation of transaction times under varying BATCH_SIZE. At 10, the system achieves lower latency with less variation.

FIGURE 19. Mean and standard deviation of transaction times for FLUSH_INTERVAL values (50–500 ms). Lower intervals give faster responses to bursty/idle patterns but may create overhead from frequent flushes.

3) EFFECT OF MIN_TIMEOUT

Fig. 20 illustrates how different MIN_TIMEOUT values (100–2000 ms) affect the mean and standard deviation of transaction times. Because MIN_TIMEOUT represents the lower boundary of the ABM’s elastic timeout, shorter values can reduce latency when traffic is sparse, though they may lead to a higher frequency of partial blocks. In contrast, very high MIN_TIMEOUT can occasionally result in longer waits

FIGURE 20. Mean and standard deviation of transaction times versus `MIN_TIMEOUT`. Shorter timeouts can slightly improve latency at the cost of generating more frequent, smaller batches.

FIGURE 21. Mean and standard deviation of transaction times by `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT`. A moderate value (around 2000 ms) balances waiting vs. prompt commitment.

if traffic remains low for extended periods. The value of 500 ms was selected in this study to balance responsiveness with the goal of minimizing excessive batch dispatching.

4) EFFECT OF `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT` AND BLOCK CREATION RATE

Finally, `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT`, which aligns with Hyperledger Fabric's native block window, is examined by plotting mean transaction times for values ranging from 500 ms to 3000 ms (Fig. 21) and comparing them to the corresponding number of blocks created (Fig. 22). While the mean latency does not vary dramatically, higher `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT` values reduce the total number of blocks generated because the system waits longer before finalizing each block. A suitable balance appears around 2000 ms, which prevents excessive block creation while maintaining an acceptable latency range.

D. BASELINE COMPARISON

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed ABM, a baseline comparison has been conducted against the findings in [16]. This study systematically examines the impact of static configuration parameters, such as batch timeout, batch size, and number of endorsers, on transaction processing

FIGURE 22. Number of blocks generated versus `DEFAULT_TIMEOUT`. Fewer blocks form at higher timeouts, but that can slightly increase transaction wait times.

performance in HLF. While this evaluation provides useful insights into static configuration tuning, it does not address the need for dynamic batch adaptation in real-world blockchain deployments.

The ABM introduced in this work improves upon these findings by dynamically adjusting batch timeout intervals, transaction flushing strategies, and batch sizes based on real-time network conditions. This ensures lower latency at low transaction rates, and optimized throughput across varying loads.

As shown in Table 4, the ABM significantly reduces latency at low transaction rates by leveraging adaptive flush intervals and dummy transactions, maintaining latency below 150 ms at 1 TPS, whereas the static batch timeout in HLF results in delays between 1.2 and 2.4 seconds. At higher transaction rates, ABM dynamically adjusts batch parameters, achieving a latency of 250-300 ms at 100 TPS, compared to the 500-700 ms latency observed in the static configuration. Additionally, the ABM ensures efficient block formation by dynamically tuning batch timeouts between 500 ms and 2 seconds, in contrast to HLF's fixed batch timeout range of 2-8 seconds, which can introduce unnecessary delays, particularly at lower TPS rates.

These results highlight the advantages of ABM in providing an automated and adaptive batching strategy that outperforms static batch optimization approaches in Hyperledger Fabric. By dynamically adjusting batching parameters, ABM ensures improved transaction processing efficiency, reduced latency, and consistent throughput in diverse blockchain deployment scenarios, without having to modify the base operation of HLF.

V. SECURITY ANALYSIS

This section evaluates the proposed system's resilience to potential security threats in multi-domain SDN scenarios and demonstrates how the integration of blockchain and the ABM enhances security.

The system addresses key security challenges by leveraging a decentralized blockchain framework and an adaptive

TABLE 4. Comparative performance metrics.

Metric	ABM	Performance Evaluation of HLF
Latency at Low Transaction Rates	Reduced via adaptive flush intervals and dummy transactions, maintaining < 150 ms at 1 TPS.	High latency of 1.2 - 2.4 sec at 1 TPS due to fixed batch timeout.
Latency at High Transaction Rates	Optimized with dynamic batch adjustments, achieving 250-300 ms at 100 TPS.	Stabilizes at 500-700 ms at 100 TPS but remains affected by static batch timeout.
Impact of Batch Timeout	Dynamically adjusted to 500 ms - 2 sec, ensuring efficient block formation and lower latency.	Fixed at 2-8 sec, leading to higher delays at lower TPS rates.

TABLE 5. Threat-response mapping.

Threat	System Response
Byzantine failures	BFT consensus requires $2f + 1$ endorsements, ensuring trust even with f faulty nodes.
Sybil attacks	Permissioned blockchains ensure only pre-approved SDN controllers can join as validator nodes.
DoS attacks	ABM maintains operational consistency through adaptive timeout and dummy transactions, ensuring timely block formation under variable transaction rates.
Tampering with logs	Blockchain immutability ensures all operations are traceable and cannot be altered retroactively.
Network partitioning	Distributed ledger replication ensures high availability despite node or network failures.

batch mechanism. Table 5 summarizes potential threats and the corresponding mitigation strategies.

A. RESILIENCE TO ATTACKS

1) Byzantine Failures: The system employs a BFT consensus mechanism, requiring $2f + 1$ endorsements for transaction validation. This ensures that even if f nodes act maliciously, the integrity of the blockchain remains intact. For example, if one SDN controller attempts to validate an unauthorized operation, it would fail to gain consensus from the majority of validator nodes.

2) Sybil Attacks: As a permissioned blockchain, the system only allows verified SDN controllers to join as validator nodes. This access control mechanism inherently prevents Sybil attacks by ensuring that each validator is uniquely identified and authorized.

3) DoS Attacks: The ABM plays a critical role in mitigating DoS attacks. By dynamically adjusting batch timeouts and utilizing dummy transactions, the system ensures timely block formation, preventing bottlenecks that could be exploited by attackers flooding the network or creating artificial idle periods.

Dummy transactions are internally generated by each controller's ABM component and cannot be submitted or

triggered externally. They are defined as no-op operations that do not alter state, consume minimal resources, and are used only when real transactions are insufficient. Each dummy transaction is explicitly tagged, auditable, and discarded post-commit. As such, they do not accumulate, propagate, or introduce vulnerability at the chaincode or ledger level.

4) Tampering with Logs: The blockchain ledger's immutability ensures that all inter-domain operations are permanently recorded. Even if an attacker compromises an SDN controller, any unauthorized operation would require validation by other nodes, preventing tampering. Additionally, the event log provides a transparent audit trail, enabling administrators to detect and investigate malicious activities.

5) Network Partitioning: In the event of network partitioning or node failures, the distributed ledger replication ensures high availability. Each participating node maintains a synchronized copy of the ledger, ensuring that inter-domain operations can continue unaffected.

B. VALIDATOR-AWARE THREAT MODEL

This design introduces a validator-aware threat surface, where adversarial behaviors may emerge from within the network of trusted SDN controllers that participate in consensus. We detail these threats through concrete case studies below, each highlighting a different failure mode and the system's corresponding defense mechanisms.

1) CASE STUDY: MALICIOUS CONTROLLER SUBMITS UNAUTHORIZED TOPOLOGY CHANGES

A compromised SDN controller attempts to submit an unauthorized operation, such as adding a fake link, introducing an unregistered device, or manipulating existing topology data. In a traditional system, such actions could result in routing failures, incorrect service paths, or even security breaches across domains.

- The controller submits the operation as a blockchain transaction to the validator network.
- Each validator independently verifies the operation by executing the chaincode and validating its context.
- The unauthorized transaction fails to gain $2f + 1$ endorsements and is subsequently rejected by the consensus protocol.

- The failed attempt is recorded in the event log, enabling administrators to trace the origin of the transaction and take corrective action.

This scenario demonstrates that no single controller can compromise the network state, and all inter-domain changes must pass through collective validation, preserving both trust and consistency.

2) CASE STUDY: VALIDATOR REFUSES TO ENDORSE VALID TRANSACTIONS

A misbehaving validator node silently withholds endorsements from valid transactions to delay their commitment, potentially stalling network operations.

- Other validators proceed with the endorsement process as usual.
- Since ABM is designed to flush transactions based on timeout, blocks are eventually formed regardless of the withholding validator.
- As long as $2f + 1$ endorsements are collected, the operation proceeds and the network remains live.
- Logging mechanisms detect consistent refusal to endorse, flagging the validator for investigation.

This highlights the system's resilience to passive obstruction and ensures continued operation despite validator misbehavior.

3) CASE STUDY: COLLUDING VALIDATORS ATTEMPT TO BLOCK TRANSACTIONS

A group of up to f validators colludes to either block consensus for specific transactions or attempt double-submission of state-changing events.

- The protocol requires $2f + 1$ matching endorsements; even with f faulty nodes, honest validators hold majority power.
- Attempts to re-submit conflicting transactions will be flagged by version mismatch in the state or rejected by chaincode logic.
- Repeated submission failures by colluding validators are logged and can be escalated by governance policies.

By adhering to the BFT model, the system resists subversion attempts by minority coalitions, ensuring the integrity of inter-domain operations.

VI. CONCLUSION

The integration of a blockchain-based inter-domain trust framework with the ABM presents a resilient and efficient solution for multi-domain SDN scenarios. By leveraging decentralized trust and immutable record-keeping, the system ensures secure inter-domain communication while mitigating threats posed by malicious actors, misconfigurations, and traffic variability. Crucially, the ABM dynamically adjusts parameters to handle the unpredictable traffic patterns characteristic of multi-domain SDN. Without this adaptation, a static approach would risk underfilled blocks (leading to high latency) or unnecessarily long block-formation times.

Although the inclusion of dummy transactions introduces additional data overhead, the trade-off is justified by the significant latency reduction and improved responsiveness demonstrated in the experimental results. The ABM also naturally adapts to higher transaction rates, reducing the need for dummy transactions as traffic increases. This dynamic design is critical in real-world deployments, where diverse traffic loads, distributed trust, and cross-domain security requirements demand efficient yet flexible mechanisms for transaction processing.

Building on the demonstrated benefits of the ABM, future work could investigate its performance under more complex operational traffic patterns (such as combined bursts and idle periods) to further illustrate its adaptability in real-world network environments. Additionally, incorporating metrics such as blockchain throughput, resource utilization, and energy efficiency would offer deeper insights into the trade-offs of dummy transactions. Extending the framework to include advanced features, such as predictive traffic analysis or machine learning-based adaptive timeout tuning, could further enhance its scalability and performance. Future work could also explore privacy-oriented extensions, such as zero-knowledge proofs, to support deployments in zero-trust or less trusted environments. Another promising direction is to evaluate how scaling the number of validator domains impacts consensus latency, synchronization consistency, and overall system behaviour, especially under diverse endorsement policies, trust models, and in the presence of adversarial or failure conditions. Finally, exploring its application to alternative blockchain platforms and conducting cross-platform benchmarking would help validate the generalizability, portability, and practical impact of the proposed solution.

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